

Correction to: Health outcomes in COPD smokers using heated tobacco products: a 3-year follow-up

Riccardo Polosa^{1,2,3,9} · Jaymin B. Morjaria⁴ · Umberto Prosperini⁵ · Barbara Busà⁶ · Alfio Pennisi⁷ · Gualberto Gussoni⁸ · Sonja Rust³ · Marilena Maglia^{1,2} · Pasquale Caponnetto^{1,2,3}

Published online: 30 June 2022
© The Author(s), 2022

Correction to: Internal and Emergency Medicine <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11739-021-02674-3>

In the acknowledgment section for JBM in the original publication of the article, the donation was not made to ASH but various charities. Hence, the correct sentence should read as “All proceeds of the work were donated to a number of charities”.

The original article has been corrected.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source,

provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Publisher's Note Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

The original article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11739-021-02674-3>.

✉ Riccardo Polosa
polosa@unict.it

¹ Department of Clinical and Experimental Medicine, University of Catania, Catania, Italy

² Centre for the Prevention and Treatment of Tobacco Addiction (CPCT), Teaching Hospital “Policlinico-V. Emanuele”, University of Catania, Catania, Italy

³ Center of Excellence for the Acceleration of Harm Reduction (CoEHAR), Università di Catania, Catania, Italy

⁴ Department of Respiratory Medicine, Royal Brompton and Harefield Hospital Foundation Trust, Harefield Hospital, Harefield, UK

⁵ Hospital “San Vincenzo”, Taormina, Italy

⁶ UOC Farmacia Ospedaliera, Hospital ARNAS Garibaldi, Catania, Italy

⁷ Department of Respiratory Medicine, Hospital Clinics “Musumeci-Gecas”, Catania, Italy

⁸ Department for Clinical Research “Centro Studi” FADOI (Scientific Society of Internal Medicine), Milan, Italy

⁹ UOC Medicina Interna e Urgenza, AOU “Policlinico-V. Emanuele-San Marco”, Via S. Sofia, 78-Ed. 4, p. 2, Stanza 78, 95100 Catania, Italy